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Institutional Policies And Procedures For Managing Digital Learning In Public Universities In Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated institutional policies and procedures for managing digital learning in universities in Rivers State. Two (2) objectives, two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The design of the study was descriptive survey design. The population of the study was 199 Head of Departments from the three universities in Rivers State (University of Port Harcourt 88, Rivers State University 78 and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education 33) and sample was the entire 199 head of departments from the same universities while the sampling technique were census and stratified random sampling techniques. The instrument adopted for data gathering was a self-designed 10 items scale titled “Institutional Policies and Procedures for Managing Digital Learning Questionnaire” (IPPMDL) and reliability coefficients of 0.82 was established which showed that the instrument was reliable. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while the hypotheses tested using z-test at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed different institutional policies such as academic policies, communication policies, staff development policies etc for managing digital learning in public Universities Rivers State. Hence, it was concluded that, institutional policies and procedures are very important and needed for managing digital learning in public Universities in Rivers State. It was recommended that there should be institutional policies such as academic policies, communication policies etc. and procedures which will serve as guide for managing digital learning in public Universities in Rivers State.

Keywords: Digital learning, Institutional polices, institutional procedures, management.

INTRODUCTION

Digital learning has become a recurring theme in contemporary learning environment in Nigeria. Before now, learning was done the traditional way. This refers to the teacher speaks—learners listen approach. With the rise in computer technology and its incorporation into learning, there have been attempts at transition from the traditional method into digital learning. The implication of such transition bears the burden of creating policies and procedures, not only for its application in learning, but also its management cum sustenance. Policies are blueprints for a sustainable process in achieving a goal through a set up system while procedures are step-by-step approaches targeted at ensuring proper implementation of laid-down policies. Policies are necessary to create a mean between two extremes—the departure from

the former learning method and the full embrace of the new. Certain factors border around creating the experience of digital learning such as finance, human capacity building, constant orientation/re-orientation, infrastructure, initiative, adaptability to local environment, utility and local resourcefulness, adaptation to possible new trends, global competence and general system maintenance. These issues are central to the success of managing digital learning in universities in Rivers state. *Ipsa facto*, it is crucial that veritable policies and procedures be created to ensure they all take their appropriate places in the management of digital learning. The digitization of education involves students using mobile and internet technology, broadening their knowledge and extending their bounds. Students develop new abilities required for success in the 21st century through the effective use of digital technology, the engagement of education seekers in independent research the choice of information and participation in project activities (Alenezi, 2023). Digital learning, often referred to as e-learning or online learning, encompasses a broad array of instructional practices that utilize digital tools and resources to facilitate and enhance the educational experience. The concept of digital learning includes not only the delivery of content through digital platforms but also interactive and engaging activities that support the learning process. It integrates various forms of technology, including the internet, multimedia, and mobile devices, to provide learners with flexible and personalized educational opportunities.

Furthermore, digital learning has many sides and shades according to the educational problems it is set out to mitigate. Hence, policies and procedures are expected to be tailored along diverse educational interests and parameters. Digital learning affects virtually every aspect of human learning. It becomes imperative to create a system that uniquely focuses on specific learning objectives in each area. For instance, digital learning in Rivers state could centre on linguistic learning. This will take cognizance of the unique learning approaches in the digital world suitable for the problems to be solved in the area. A good instance is creating sub-policies aimed at fighting the rise of Pidgin English among students in universities. With this in mind, the target population to be imparted, the work force, the implements, implementation process, technological approaches, time factor and so on, forms the basis for such approach. It is also noteworthy that this approach to learning requires a synergy between the technology-expert and the content-expert. While the former concentrates on the digital means of solving learning problems, the latter dwells on the learning problems and issues surrounding them; theoretical or practical. Creation of policies obviously has inherent challenges. This ranges from time factor, human factor, environment analysis, maintenance and so on. A good policy is the one that intrinsically captures more satisfactorily, the solutions to these challenges. The state government has a huge role to play in this as no aspect of a state's progress can go really far without the support of the government and alignment with her goals. There must therefore be a synchrony between the long term goals of the state and the goals of digital learning. In fact, the goals of digital learning should be so drawn that the policies mirror the aspiration of the state. There will also be a need for collaborative efforts outside the state to learn, borrow, synergize and interact on the digital learning platforms. This should form a crucial part of the policies as no man is an island. Digital learning should have such policies that it should make learners in our universities to turn out as locally useful and globally competent citizens. It should include a view of tackling the problems of unemployment and wealth creation.

Clark and Mayer (2016) define digital learning as "the use of digital technologies to deliver, support, and enhance teaching, learning, and assessment." They emphasize the integration of multimedia elements such as text, audio, video, and interactive simulations to create an engaging learning environment.

Similarly, Bates (2019) describes digital learning as "the use of information and communication technologies to support and enhance learning and teaching." Bates highlights the importance of accessibility and flexibility, noting that digital learning allows learners to access educational materials at their convenience, regardless of their geographical location.

The adoption of digital learning has seen significant growth globally. According to a report by the Global Market Insights (2021), the e-learning market size surpassed USD 250 billion in 2020 and is projected to grow at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of over 21% from 2021 to 2027. This growth is driven

by the increasing demand for flexible learning solutions, advancements in technology, and the need for continuous education in a rapidly changing world.

Importance of Digital Learning in Higher Education:

Digital learning has become a cornerstone of modern higher education, transforming how knowledge is delivered, accessed, and consumed. The shift towards digital learning is driven by its potential to provide flexible, inclusive, and innovative educational experiences. Here, we explore the importance of digital learning in higher education, comparing the views of various authors and presenting relevant statistics and facts to support these perspectives.

Flexibility and Accessibility:

One of the most significant advantages of digital learning is its flexibility. According to Bates (2019), digital learning allows students to access course materials and participate in learning activities at their convenience, making education more accessible to those who may have work, family, or other commitments. This flexibility is particularly beneficial for non-traditional students, such as working professionals or those with caregiving responsibilities.

Clark and Mayer (2016) also highlight that digital learning platforms can provide access to a wealth of resources and materials that might not be available locally. This democratization of education enables students from diverse backgrounds to gain access to high-quality educational content, regardless of their geographical location.

Enhanced Engagement and Interaction:

Digital learning tools, such as interactive simulations, virtual labs, and gamified learning experiences, can significantly enhance student engagement. Means et al. (2013) found that online learning environments that incorporate interactive elements can improve student motivation and participation compared to traditional classroom settings. These tools make learning more dynamic and can help to sustain student interest over time.

Cost-Effectiveness:

From an institutional perspective, digital learning can be more cost-effective than traditional face-to-face instruction. According to a study by the Online Learning Consortium (OLC) (2016), universities can reduce costs associated with physical infrastructure, such as classroom space and maintenance, by implementing digital learning solutions. Additionally, digital learning can support larger class sizes without compromising educational quality, further enhancing cost efficiency.

Scalability and Reach:

Digital learning platforms allow institutions to scale their offerings and reach a global audience. Bates (2019) emphasizes that universities can offer massive open online courses (MOOCs) and other online programs to students worldwide, expanding their reach and impact. This scalability is crucial for institutions aiming to increase their global presence and attract a diverse student body.

Compliance Bridge (2022) identifies the following policies and procedures for universities:

Academic Policies: These policies and procedures are meant to guide students, faculty and other staff as they navigate the most common academic tasks such as adding or dropping courses, declaring or changing majors, withdrawing from classes, and also, there should be academic policies that define minimum scholastic requirements. If a student does not meet the requirements and must be put on academic probation, you need to be prepared with a policy outlining this process to ensure it remains fair. Other matters of academic misconducts should be addressed with a formal policy as well. These include disrupting class, plagiarism, cheating, falsifying research results, forging signatures, etc.

Communication Policies:

Universities are often tasked with providing important campus updates to students, parents, faculty and staff and to make sure they do so effectively, formal policies and procedures are need for effective communication.

Information Technology Policies:

Universities have sophisticated computer system, networks and information resources that thousands of students, faculty and staff use everyday which are supposed to be properly guided and monitored.

Non-Academic Misconduct Policies:

Campus safety and the wellbeing of students is a huge concern for higher institutions. Higher educational institutions have a responsibility to provide a safe living and learning environment for students, staff, faculty and anyone else who is on their grounds. When an incident occurs that negatively affects the campus environment, university policies and procedures that can help one must be prepared that will help one effectively address it.

Also, Ogunode, et al (2020) identify different education policies and level of implementation in Nigerian higher institutions using universities education as case study:

- Recruitment policies – entry qualifications, professionalism and welfare
- Staff development policies
- Infrastructural facilities policies
- Lecturers-students ratio policies

Recruitment Policies:

According to the National Universities Commission (NUC) policies on recruitment into the universities are: Minimum entry qualification of a teaching staff into polytechnic is Bachelor's degree in relevant field. In Colleges of Education, the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) requires that candidates to be considered for appointment should have, besides first degree, acquire some qualification in education. This means that they have to be certified as professional teachers. The minimum academic qualification required for appointing a university teacher in Nigeria is Master's Degree.

Occasionally, 'persons who have high quality Bachelor's degrees are given positions of Assistant Lecturer', while sometimes, "those who have Second Class (Honours) Upper Division are given the job of a Graduate Assistant" according to Mgbekem in Ogunode (2020).

Staff Development Policies:

Government emphasised in the National Policy on Education to encourage all teachers in tertiary institutions to undergo training in the methods and techniques of teaching. As a result of this, some teachers in the universities who are not certified teachers have enrolled for courses leading to the award of a Post-Graduate Diploma in Education (PGDE) (NUC, in Ogunode 2020).

Infrastructural Facilities Policies:

According to the National Universities Commission Benchmark Policies in Ogunode (2020) stated that adequate lecturers' offices, classrooms, functional and well adequate equipped language laboratory, soundproof rooms and studios etc. The policies also stated that lecturers will be given good office accommodation, provision of necessary tools such as desktop, laptop, scanner, printer, internet facilities.

Lecturers-students Ratio Policies:

The National Universities Commission Benchmark Minimum Academic Standards (BMAS) of 2007 stipulated the following teacher/students ratio: 1:20 in science; 1:15 in Engineering and Technology: 1:10 in medicine, etc.

Smith College (2024) in the same vein identifies the following institutional procedures:

Procedures: These are necessary steps to drive the policies stated already. The procedures are on three strata.

Phase one: This will be at two levels: Quantitative and qualitative levels.

Quantitative level: This requires that firstly, a team be raised to start up data analysis. This involves a data on the universities; the number of lecturers, students, peculiarity of departments, availability facilities for digital infrastructure and so on.

Qualitative level: This involves ascertaining the level of digital awareness, attitudes to digital means of learning and level of technical know-how and ability to use the computer/internet of students, lecturers and other staff.

The essence of this exercise is to confirm the level of awareness, training, infrastructure and financial investment required to carry out digital learning across the universities.

Phase two: This is the implementation process that involves carrying out the necessary infrastructure, trainings and actual application of digital learning in the universities in Rivers State.

Phase three: This is the feedback system that ensure sustenance, correction, adaptation and reinvention over a period of time in the implementation process

For the purpose of this study, three Universities in Rivers State were used. They are: University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. University of Port Harcourt has 14 faculties with 88 departments (Nairaland Forum, 2024), Rivers State University has 12 faculties with 78 departments (RSU Admission Guide, 2024). Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the other hand has 6 faculties with 33 departments (IAUE, 2024).

Yushau and Khan (2020) write on digital learning management in Nigerian Universities: Challenges and prospects. Two (2) objectives, Two (2) research questions and two (2) hypotheses guided the study. The design of the study were both surveys and interviews survey designs. The population of the study was 270 students, (Comprise 200 students, 50 faculty members and 20 administrative staff members respectively). The instruments were structured questionnaires, and semi-structured interview. Reliability of the questionnaire was established using Cronbach Alpha with an index of 0.78 while the content validity was ensured by expert review. Data was analysed with descriptive statistics and regression analysis. The findings revealed that, inadequate infrastructure, lack of digital literacy and resistance to change were the major challenges identified. Also, the benefits include increased flexibility in learning and improved access to educational resources. The study concluded that, although digital learning faces significant challenges but its potential benefits make it a worthwhile investment. Based on the study, the findings recommended among others that, there should be increase funding for digital infrastructure and implementation of regular training programmes for faculty and students.

In the same vein, Adebisi and Olaniran (2018) write on the impact of digital learning policies on student engagement in Nigerian higher educations. Two (2) objectives, two (2) research questions and two (2) hypotheses guided the study. The design was quantitative study using surveys. Students from five Universities in Nigeria were used as population while 500 students were selected through stratified random sampling. The instrument for the study was structured questionnaires. Cronbach alpha coefficient was established at 0.81 while the content validity was ensured by expert review. The research questions were answered by descriptive statistics while the hypotheses was analysed by inferential statistics (regression analysis). The result showed that digital learning policies are essential for enhancing students' engagement and that technical support and faculty training are crucial for the success of these policies. The study concluded that, effective digital learning policies are essential for enhancing students' engagement. Based on the findings, the study recommended among others that, technical support should be enhanced for digital learning and there should be regular review and update digital learning policies.

Odukoya et al (2019) investigate challenges and opportunities in implementing digital learning in Nigerian Universities. Two (2) objectives, two (2) research questions and two (2) hypotheses were used for the study respectively. The research design was descriptive and the population consists of faculty and administrative staff from four Universities in Nigeria while 40 participants were selected as sample (10 from each university). The instrument that was semi-structured interview guides. Thematic analysis was used to analyse data. The findings revealed that, challenges include lack of infrastructure, digital literacy and funding while opportunities include partnerships with tech companies and international organizations. It was concluded that, there are numerous opportunities to improve digital learning despite significant challenges. The study recommended among others that, there should be increase funding for digital learning initiatives while strengthen partnerships with technology providers.

Eze et al, (2020) write on determinants of digital learning adoption among Nigerian Universities. Two (2) objectives, two (2) research questions and two (2) hypotheses guided the study respectively. The research design were surveys and focus group discussions. The population for the study was 550 participants (400

students and 150 faculty members. Structured questionnaires and focus group discussion guides were used as instruments. Reliability coefficients of 0.83 was established using Cronbach alpha. Content validity was ensured by expert review and pilot testing descriptive and inferential statistics (regression analysis) were used to answer research questions while thematic analysis was used for hypotheses. The results showed that, institutional support and faculty training are significant determinants of digital learning adoption. Hence, It was concluded that, effective adoption of digital learning requires strong institutional support and continuous faculty development. It was recommended that institutional support for digital learning initiatives should be enhanced and there should be provision of regular and comprehensive training for faculty members.

Olumide and Ogundipe (2021) investigate barriers to effective implementation of digital learning in Nigerian higher education institutions. Two (2) objectives, two (2) research questions and two (2) hypotheses were used for the study respectively. The design was descriptive and the population consists of faculty and administrative staff from four Universities in Nigeria while the sample was 40 participants (10 from each University). Semi- Structural interview was the instrument used for the study. Thematic analysis was used for data analysis. The result showed that major barriers include inadequate infrastructure, lack of funding, limited digital literacy and resistance to change. It was concluded that, continuous support and training are crucial for the successful implementation of digital learning. The study recommended among others that, the government should invest in digital infrastructure and resource as well as providing ongoing training and support for faculty and students

Statement of the Problem

Implementation of digital learning requires strong workable policies and procedures to help mitigate the issues of migration from former traditional learning approaches to digital method, infrastructural needs, compliance of all concerned, sustenance of contemporary learning approaches, achieving educational efficiency, attainment of Rivers state educational goals, creation of synergy and platforms that unites lecturers and learners in universities in Rivers state with their counterparts without, in thoughts, developmental progress and interaction. There is also need to channel and harness the vast digital platforms in a way that it becomes a more profitable asset to learning. The fact that many older lecturers are digital immigrants also requires that policies be tailored to include them in a way that the purpose of digital learning is not compromised. However, there is limited empirical research on the existing institutional policies and procedures for managing digital learning in universities within Rivers State. Without a clear understanding of these policies and procedures, it is difficult to identify gaps and areas for improvement. Additionally, the perspectives of males and female heads of departments on these policies and procedures may differ, and such differences need to be explored to ensure inclusive and equitable digital learning environments. Hence, this study seeks to address these gaps by investigating the current institutional policies and procedures for managing digital learning in universities in Rivers State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The study investigated the institutional policies and procedures for managing digital learning in Universities in Rivers State. Specifically, the objectives of the study were to:

1. determine institutional policies for managing digital learning in Universities in Rivers State.
2. ascertain procedures for managing digital learning in Universities in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What are the institutional policies for managing digital learning in Universities in Rivers State?
2. What are the institutional procedures for managing digital learning in Universities in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level:

1. There is no significant difference between the opinion of mean rating of male and female heads of department on the institutional policies for managing digital learning in Universities in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant difference between the opinion of mean rating of male and female heads of department on the institutional procedures for managing digital learning in Universities in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The design for the study was descriptive, the population was 199 male and female head of departments in the public universities in Rivers State, which the same 199 male and female head of departments were used as sampled while the sampling techniques were census and stratified. The instrument used to collect data for the study was scale which was validated. Institutional Policies and Procedure for Managing Digital Learning' (IPPMDL) with reliability index of 0.82 obtained using Cronbach alpha mathematical technique. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions while z-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of statistical significance.

RESULTS

Research Question Five: *What are the institutional policies for managing digital learning in Universities in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Mean scores and standard deviation of male and female respondents on the institutional policies for managing digital learning in Universities in Rivers State.

SN	Institutional Policies for Managing Digital Learning Variable	Respondents				Mean Set $\bar{X}_1\bar{X}_2$	Decision
		Male = 118 \bar{X}_1	SD ₁	Female = 81 \bar{X}_2	SD ₂		
1	Academic policies are meant to guide students, faculty and other staff misconduct.	2.89	0.98	3.28	0.76	3.08	Agreed
2	Communication policies such as campus updates to students, faculty and staff are necessary.	2.83	0.77	2.89	0.88	2.86	Agreed
3	Information technology policies such as Sophisticated computer system, networks and information resources are necessary in higher instructions policies.	3.20	0.74	3.29	0.69	3.24	Agreed
4	Infrastructural facilities policies are necessary for faculty and students well-being.	2.82	0.92	2.63	1.03	2.72	Agreed
5	Staff development policies enable all the lecturers in the Universities to become a certified teachers.	3.12	0.68	2.58	0.74	2.85	Agreed
Average Mean/Standard Deviation		2.97	0.82	2.93	0.82	2.95	

Data on Table 1: with the mean scores and standard deviation of male and female respondents on the institutional policies for managing digital learning in Universities in Rivers State. The results item academic policies, communication policies, information technology policies, infrastructural facilities policies and staff development policies with the mean score of 3.08, 2.86, 3.24, 2.72 and 2.85 respectively, having the average mean scores are 2.97 for the male and 2.93 for the female. Based on the

average mean set score of 2.95 which is above the criterion mean of 2.50, it implies that both male and female respondents agreed on item academic policies, communication policies, information technology policies, infrastructural facilities policies and staff development policies as the institutional policies for managing digital learning in Universities in Rivers State.

Research Question Two: *What are the institutional procedures for managing digital learning in Universities in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Mean scores and standard deviation of male and female respondents on the institutional procedures for managing digital learning in Universities in Rivers State.

SN	Institutional Procedures for Managing Digital Learning Variable	Respondents				Mean Set $\bar{X}_1\bar{X}_2$	Decision
		Male = 118		Female =81			
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂		
6	Academic misconduct policies can be implemented through recruitments of well experienced security officers.	2.86	0.81	2.93	0.70	2.75	Agreed
7	Effective communication of important campus update through social media, whatsapp etc will ensure implementation of communication policies.	3.17	0.85	3.11	0.86	3.08	Agreed
8	Raising a team to start up data analysis for lecturers, students etc will ensure the implementation of Information Technology Policies	3.19	0.90	3.09	0.87	3.14	Agreed
9	Ascertaining the level of digital awareness, level of technical-know-how and ability to use the computer/internet by students, lecturers and other staff reveals the level of implementation of infrastructural facilities.	2.78	0.91	2.94	0.89	2.72	Agreed
10	Undergoing training in the methods and techniques of teaching will enable all the teachers in tertiary institutions to become 'certified teachers'	3.18	0.69	3.19	0.87	3.17	Agreed
Average Mean/Standard Deviation		3.03	0.83	3.05	0.84	3.04	

Data on Table 2: with the mean scores and standard deviation of male and female respondents on the institutional procedures for managing digital learning in Universities in Rivers State. The results item 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10, with the mean score of 2.75, 3.08, 3.14, 2.72 and 3.17 respectively, having the average mean scores are 3.03 for the male and 3.05 for the female. Based on the average mean set score of 3.04 which is above the criterion mean of 2.50, it implies that both male and female respondents agreed on item 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10 as the institutional procedures for managing digital learning in Universities in Rivers State.

Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the opinion of mean rating of male and female heads of department on the institutional policies for managing digital learning in Universities in Rivers State.

Table 3: z-test Analysis on the difference between the opinion of mean rating of male and female heads of department on the institutional policies for managing digital learning in Universities in Rivers State.

Category	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	z-cal	z-crit.	Remarks
Male	118	2.97	0.82	197	0.338	±1.96	Not Significant
Female	81	2.93	0.82				Accepted H ₀₁ (z-cal. > z-crit.)
Total	199						

Table 3 with the average mean scores and standard deviation of male and female respondents stood at 2.97 and 0.82 and 2.93 and 0.82 respectively. Simple observation show that these mean scores are closely related, and suggest no significant difference.

Furthermore, since at 197 degree of freedom and at 0.05 alpha level of significance, the calculated z-test value of 0.338 was far less than the z-critical value of 1.96, we were constrained to Accept the null hypothesis and established that, there is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female heads of department on the institutional policies for managing digital learning in Universities in Rivers State.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the opinion of mean rating of male and female heads of department on the institutional procedures for managing digital learning in Universities in Rivers State.

Table 4: z-test Analysis on the difference between the opinion of mean rating of male and female heads of department on the institutional procedures for managing digital learning in Universities in Rivers State.

Category	N	\bar{X}	SD	df	z-cal	z-crit.	Remarks
Male	118	3.05	0.83	197	-0.17	-1.96	Significant
Female	81	3.03	0.84				Rejected H ₀₂ (z-cal. < z-crit.)
Total	199						

Table 4. with the average mean rating and standard deviation of male and female respondents stood at 3.03 and 0.83 and 3.05 and 0.84 respectively. Simple observation show that these mean scores are closely related, and suggest a significant difference. Furthermore, since at 197 degree of freedom and at 0.05 alpha level of significance, the calculated z-test value of -0.17 was far greater than the z-critical table value of -1.96, we accept the null hypothesis and established that, there is a significant difference between the mean rating of male and female heads of department on the institutional procedures for managing digital learning in Universities in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The result of the study showed that the respondents averagely agreed to the items listed as the institutional policies for managing digital learning in public Universities in Rivers State. The study revealed that there

was no significant difference between the opinion of male and female heads of departments on the institutional policies for managing digital learning in public Universities in Rivers State. This study agrees with the outcome of the study by Adebisi and Olaniran (2018) which showed that digital learning policies are essential for enhancing students' engagement and that technical support and faculty training are crucial for success of these policies the heads of departments in their responses agreed that sophisticated computer system, networks and information resources are properly installed in higher institutions. Also, the respondents agreed that staff development policies enable all the lecturers in the Universities to become a certified teachers which is in agreement with Eze et al (2020) who stated that, institutional support and faculty training are significant determinants of digital learning adoption.

The result also showed that, the respondents agreed to the items listed as the institutional procedures for managing digital learning in public Universities in Rivers State. The study showed that there was no significant difference between the opinion of male and female heads of departments on the institutional procedures for managing digital learning in public Universities in Rivers State. The respondents agreed that undergoing training in the methods and techniques of teaching will enable all the teachers in tertiary institutions to become 'certified teachers'. This is in agreement with what Alenezi, 2023 said that students develop new abilities required for success in the 21st century through effective use of digital technology. Likewise, Olumide and Ogundipe (2021) stated in their study that, continuous support and training are crucial for the successful implementation of digital learning. Also, the heads of departments agreed that raising a team to start up data analysis for lecturers, students etc will ensure the implementation of information technology policies. This is in agreement with what Odukoya et al (2019) stated in their study that, there are numerous opportunities to improve digital learning despite significant challenges.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded based on the findings that, institutional policies such as academic policies, communication policies, information technology policies, infrastructural facilities policies and staff development policies and procedures are very important and needed for managing digital learning in public Universities in Rivers State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were proffered on the findings of the study;

1. There should be institutional policies such as academic policies, communication policies, information technology policies, infrastructural facilities policies and staff development policies for managing digital learning in public Universities in Rivers State.
2. There should be procedures (steps) to drive those policies for managing digital learning in public Universities in Rivers State.

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